

DIDACTIC OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP HEALTHY LIFESTYLE SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Although the problems of the formation of a healthy lifestyle in young people have been studied from the side of various Soha scientists, however, the problem of improving the pedagogical mechanisms of the observance of the principles of continuity and continuity of the didactic possibilities of the development of life skills of a healthy lifestyle has not been studied.*

Keywords: *higher education institutions, students, healthy lifestyle, life skills, didactic, improvement. sports-wellness, research.*

Introduction. The need for pedagogical analysis of the results of scientific research, pedagogical observation, survey, comparative analysis of the results of current research and pedagogical experience, didactic opportunities for the development of a healthy lifestyle in students on the basis of scientific research on the topic of research, as well as the need for comprehensive scientific research.

Main part. In recent years in higher education institutions, in the educational system of physical education and sport educational works, improving the didactic possibilities of developing life skills of a healthy lifestyle in students, encouraging the population to work on sport-health, healthy life among students The normative basis of assessing the state of lifestyle formation and determining the problematic areas of promoting a healthy lifestyle explain the necessity of this research. The methodological approach to the study of the influence of factors determining a healthy lifestyle on the integration of students with impaired health into society is based on the study of socialization and preventive actions in relation to health, as well as personal factors of life activities, as a result of the study of health care by students and showed that it is necessary to determine the nature of behavior related to reinforcement. According to the data obtained during the research, the students themselves evaluate the importance of physical education and a healthy lifestyle as follows: "achieving the goal" (40.6%); "Improving educational activities" (32.3%); "Improving well-being" (30.7%); "To plan your time better" (20.0%); "increasing the effectiveness of communication" (11.1%). The analysis of the results of the conducted survey showed that students' motivation to study is at a high level, that is, the level of motivation has increased from an average of 92.1% to 96%. Based on the obtained results, the group of students with more than 50% results was selected as the control group, and the group of students with less than 50% results was selected as the experimental group. Increasing the effectiveness of progressive organizational-pedagogical mechanisms based on the unique characteristics of the individual approach to the self-development of life skills of a healthy lifestyle in students of higher educational institutions according to the principles of innovative educational technologies and on the basis of the intensive application of the principles of free choice of variable information-didactic resources, a model for improving the didactic possibilities of developing life skills of a healthy lifestyle was developed.

Generalized mastering indicators of experience and control groups in all academic years the level of mastery of knowledge and skills in professional science the model of the development of life skills of a healthy lifestyle in students progressive organizational and pedagogical

mechanisms on the basis of the principles of innovative educational technologies didactic possibilities were identified. In the study jaaryon, the model for the development of life skills of a healthy lifestyle in students is characterized by progressive organizational and pedagogical mechanisms based on the conceptual foundations of the development of a healthy lifestyle in students, the disclosure of the content of comronents for the development of healthy life skills in students, such other important indicators as regular physical activity (26.7 %), – disease prevention, scheduled medical examinations, etc (15.3 %) and hygiene compliance (10.9 %) were found.

In the results of the study of the component of improving the didactic possibilities of developing life skills of a healthy lifestyle in students studying in higher education institutions: the cognitive component is up to 3.52 - low, 3.53 - 5.8 - medium, 5, 9 - 7 - high level; it has been proven that the number of students with a low level of emotional component (negative attitude) is greater than the number of students with a high level (positive attitude); motivational component up to 7.13 - low, 7.14 - 9.44 - average, 9.45-10 - high level; conative component up to 5.9 - low, 6 - 8.5 - medium, 8.6 - 10 - high level, practical component up to 7 - low, 7 - 8.8 - medium, 8.8 - 10 - high level indicators were determined. Based on this, the model for the development of life skills of a healthy lifestyle in students is based on progressive organizational-edagogical mechanisms, the optimal integration of creative-motivational, reflexive-professional skills in accordance with educational tasks, as well as self-development and stimulation. The importance of professional preparation of professional subjects in the implementation of an individual approach in improving the didactic capabilities of students of physical culture education was conducted during the educational process of NamDU, UrDU, TDPU, and in general, 1.17 (17%) is twice as high as proven by statistical methods.

In conclusion, according to the results of the final test of the conducted research, the level of formation of theoretical knowledge and skills, the level of formation of design skills necessary for further use of professional sciences, and the level of motivational attitude to study in the future professional activity in the research group compared to the control group we can see that it has grown relatively.

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